

Transforming the Classroom with Mobile Learning, Applications, and Creative Programming

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Abstract – The increasing use of mobile devices in education has transformed traditional teaching and learning processes. With students already accustomed to using mobile devices for daily tasks, educators can leverage this familiarity for educational purposes, particularly in testing and assessments. Mobile-based testing and practicing offers an innovative approach to teaching and learning and makes assessments more accessible and engaging while bridging the gap between theoretical knowledge and practical skills. This article explores the benefits and challenges of implementing mobile applications in classrooms as an extra tool to help students practice and implement the course theoretical concepts. The article also highlights the educational potential of transitioning from a traditional teaching culture to a mobile application culture, implementing mobile-based applications and software development projects, and encouraging students to create apps using programming languages like Python, C++, Java, and others.

Keywords – applications, classroom, interactive, learning, mobile, programming

I. INTRODUCTION

Mobile-based testing and application development in university classrooms offer unique opportunities for enhancing student engagement, learning outcomes, and technical skills. While there are challenges to consider, the benefits of increased accessibility, instant feedback, and hands-on learning make mobile-based methods a valuable addition to modern education. By leveraging mobile technology for testing and encouraging students to create their own applications, educators can bridge the gap between theoretical knowledge and practical skills, preparing students for success in a tech-driven world [1]-[3].

Usage of mobile devices in the classroom is gaining wide popularity these days within institutions of higher education. There are, however, benefits to both learners and instructors. While there are a lot of arguments that mobile devices represent a distraction, their potential for enhancing the likelihood of positive learning outcomes and increasing engagement outperforms risks when put to appropriate uses [4], [5].

Mobile devices contribute to many advantages in higher learning institutions in terms of increased access to educational resources, facilitation of active learning, collaboration, and enhancement of digital literacy skills [6].

One of the most important of the various benefits that university mobile devices offer consists of direct access to educational resources. Students can instantly find information, acquire e-books, journal articles, databases, or apps relating to specific fields. This allows the students to clarify any concepts, get into more details, or confirm information during the lectures [7].

This can also support multimedia learning through the provision of an opportunity for students to engage in video simulations or interactive diagrams in complementing the traditional teaching materials. Mobile technology also fosters active learning, getting and retaining information, and developing problem-solving skills [8]– [10].

Because students are so comfortable with mobile devices, a mobile device becomes both a natural and effective platform on which learning can effectively occur. After all, students today access most information on mobile phones rather than from traditional textbooks; learning material is thus more familiar and accessible via mobile-based learning. Due to the large number of educational applications available on mobile phones, students will have the ability to engage in math theory, algebra, number theory, geometry, proofs, and programming—all enhancing their scholastic experience and abilities [11]. Another obvious benefit of mobile learning is the ability to learn anytime and anywhere. Such flexibility supports continuous learning beyond the classroom since students might utilize downtime or commutes to review tutorials or solve problems. Many Android applications provide step-by-step explanations, interaction exercises, and even video lessons for tutorials in mathematics and other STEM subjects. This makes learning not something constrained to lifeless textbook pages but dynamic, multimodal, and with adaptations to different learning styles [12]-[14].

Another important issue concerning mobile devices is that students should be shown how much they can benefit from these devices as tools for learning, not just for entertainment. If students can realize how much valuable information and resources are out there and accessible through their phones, they will more likely adapt to using them for academic purposes. It shows practical use and applications through mobile-based tutorials and education apps, demonstrating to students how concepts learned in class could be applied or used to solve real-life problems or develop applications [15]-[17].

Mobile technology promotes more interactive learning and applied learning for learners through their exposure to a wide variety of educational applications that introduce complicated ideas in ways most easily assimilated. Some specially designed apps and calculators for mathematics solve problems related to graph plotting, equation solving, matrix operations, optimization practices, and statistical analysis. [18]-[20].

Mobile applications enable students to examine matrix properties or solve systems of linear equations much more quickly than they could by hand or help them self-control their results. This is particularly helpful in classes such as linear algebra, where the student is working with many matrix operations and every optimization of a computational task frees class time for deeper conceptual discussions. The statistical analysis also benefits greatly from mobile technology, with many useful statistics applications that are available on Android (Play Store) or iOS (App Store) [21].

Mobile phones make it possible for students to learn at their own pace and in the most appropriate place. Several platforms, like Udemy, Coursera, and edX, have plenty of available videos on any course one wishes to pursue, whether it is mathematics, sciences, languages, or even programming.

Mobile learning platforms offer a range of courses to match various learning approaches and levels of students. Students can take an introductory class in mathematics on algebra, geometry, etc., or other deeper subjects such as number theory and the proof in mathematics. They can also view programming tutorials in languages such as Python, JavaScript, C++ or Java and other programming languages [22]-[24].

This mobile app culture ranges beyond formal education and expands into lifetime learning and professional development. Many professionals, particularly in the STEM fields, update their knowledge

concerning changes within their industries, build new skills, or get ready for certification and recognitions through mobile apps [25]-[27].

The growing availability and use of educational apps are reflective of a cultural shift to more productive uses of mobile devices. While social media still dominates how people use mobiles, the upsurge in educational and STEM-related apps is indicative of a broadening mobile culture. This, in turn, encourages users to regard mobile devices not just as forms of entertainment but as powerful means to learn, innovate, and grow professionally [28]-[30].

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

To investigate the benefits of using mobile applications and software in mathematics education, a structured survey was designed specifically for university students enrolled in STEM programs. This survey, formatted on a 5-point Likert scale (from "strongly disagree" to "strongly agree"), evaluated the frequency and perceived effectiveness of mobile tools for solving mathematical problems, enhancing conceptual learning, and facilitating practical applications [31], [32].

Key topics included the level of encouragement from educators to use mobile resources, the availability of ICT lab resources supporting mathematical and general STEM applications, and students' personal experiences and perceptions of the effectiveness of these tools. The survey also explored whether students believed that using these applications contributed to a deeper understanding of mathematics and improved their analytical and problem-solving abilities [33]-[35].

Participants included four groups of students: 60 first-year Mechanical Engineering students from the Polytechnic University of Tirana, 25 second- and third-year Mathematics and Informatics students from the University of Durrës, 20 second-year Marketing students from the same university, and 30 master's students in the M-I program, also from the University of Durrës, totaling 135 participants.

The survey was created via Google Forms and distributed through email and Google Classroom to ensure easy access and broad participation. Data were collected electronically, organized in Excel, and analyzed using descriptive statistics in Excel and SPSS 22 to identify students' attitudes toward mobile-assisted learning in mathematics.

The 11 questions were grouped into three sections:

Section 1: Promotion of Mobile and PC Applications in STEM Education

Section 2: Quality of ICT Laboratories in High School and University

Section 3: Student Interest in Software Development

Questions were as follows:

- 1) STEM (Science, Technology, Engineering, Mathematics) teachers/professors encourage us to use mobile and PC apps to better understand theory.
- 2) STEM teachers/professors often recommend specific mobile and PC apps to enhance our practical skills.
- 3) Teachers and professors show us examples of how apps can improve our learning of theory and practice.
- 4) STEM teachers/professors frequently assign tasks that require specific apps for solving problems.
- 5) Teachers/professors often use Google Classroom to give multiple-choice tests to assess our readiness.
- 6) Our ICT labs have modern computers and networks that support current STEM software and apps.
- 7) The ICT labs are equipped with updated operating systems and applications for practical learning in STEM.
- 8) Teachers and professors frequently use ICT lab resources to show how STEM concepts can be applied practically.

- 9) Using educational apps (Windows and Android) and seeing the benefits inspires me to learn about software development and consider it as a career.
- 10) University programming courses should cover more on software development, including creating “.exe” and “.apk” files, and support students in building a programming portfolio.
- 11) University programming courses should include mobile app development and promote student projects on the university website, App and Play Store, and other platforms.

The values of the questions are:

- 1 = strongly disagree,
- 2 = disagree,
- 3 = neutral,
- 4 = agree,
- 5 = strongly agree,

The interpretation of the mean values is, table 1.

Table 1. Mean values and interpretation

Mean value	Interpretation
1- 1.8	Strongly disagree (SD)
1.81- 2.6	Disagree (D)
2.61- 3.4	Neutral (N)
3.41- 4.2	Agree (A)
4.21- 5.0	Strongly Agree (SA)

III. RESULTS

The survey data gathered via e mails, was first exported to Excel via Google Form, where first statistical analyses were conducted, such as the histogram of means and the distributions of values 1-5.

Google Forms was initially exported to Excel, where preliminary visual analyses were conducted using histograms to reveal response trends. For a more professional and comprehensive analysis, the data was then imported into SPSS 22, where descriptive statistics were calculated and other important analyses such as the consistency test.

The simple descriptive analyses contain means, medians, and standard deviations for each question, for the purpose of assessing the students' attitude towards the interested topics. The consistency test is considered important to verify the reliability of the data, tables 2, 3, and figure 1.

Table 2. Descriptive statistics of data

		Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Q5	Q6	Q7	Q8	Q9	Q10	Q11
N	Valid	135	135	135	135	135	135	135	135	135	135	135
	Missing	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Mean		2.94	3.01	2.87	3.30	3.02	3.14	3.32	3.24	3.96	4.71	4.68
Median		3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	4.00	4.00	5.00	5.00
Std. Deviation		.81	.66	.85	.924	1.02	.95	.751	.980	1.16	.45	.59
Minimum		2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	2.00	2.00	4.00	3.00
Maximum		4.00	4.00	5.00	5.00	5.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	5.00	5.00	5.00
Percentiles	25	2.00	3.00	2.00	3.00	2.00	2.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	4.00	4.00
	50	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	4.00	4.00	5.00	5.00
	75	3.00	3.00	3.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	5.00	5.00	5.00

Table 3. Consistency test

Reliability Statistics		
Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
.823	.818	11

Figure 1. Distributions of answers 1-5 in all the questions

Interpretation for the Consistency Test (Cronbach’s Alpha):

A consistency test score, often interpreted as Cronbach’s alpha in survey data, indicates a high level of internal consistency among the items in surveys.

Generally:

Scores above 0.7 suggest acceptable reliability.

Scores between 0.8 and 0.9 indicate good reliability.

Scores above 0.9 suggest excellent reliability.

In our case, a score of 0.82 means that our survey items are consistently measuring the same underlying construct (e.g., students' attitudes toward using mobile applications and software in mathematics). This reliability level suggests that the survey results can be interpreted with confidence.

The interpretation for the descriptive statistics of the data for each question (Q1 to Q11) is:

The mean for each question, ranging from 2.87 (Q3) to 4.71 (Q10) indicates the average level of agreement or disagreement with each question. Generally, all the questions range from ‘neutral’ to ‘strongly agree’ (2.94–4.71), with the total average = 3.51.

The first 8 questions, which are about the level of practice and ICT laboratories, are valued in the ‘neutral’ zone, meaning that students are ‘not impressed’ with the STEM course implementation in practice, especially the use of ICT laboratories.

The three last questions have the highest assessment, meaning that the students have higher expectations from the courses.

Lower means (close to 2.87–3.32, Q1-Q8) suggest responses are more neutral or slightly disagreeable, meaning that these services are lower than the expectations.

Higher means (close to 3.96–4.71, Q9-Q11) suggest that students have higher expectations than the results or the academic services they are getting.

These values show the range of responses. All questions have responses from at least 2 to 5 (with some questions having a minimum of 1).

The data suggests that students were more neutral or mildly agreeable for the first eight questions but showed clearer agreement for the last three questions, meaning that expectations are higher than reality.

IV. CONCLUSION

Mobile devices also have a number of advantageous uses for STEM courses, whether in high school or higher education, including graph plotting, solving algebraic equations, the manipulation of matrices, analysis of statistics, and optimization exercises. In this respect, mobile technology provides the students with aids to understand mathematical concepts and other courses through APK applications, Windows or MacOS software, tutorials, and many programs that they can actually create themselves in class.

By integrating these types of resources in the classroom, teachers and professors are offering students a unique and interactive teaching and learning environment that captures the attention of students to such theoretical subjects and allows them to gather an understanding of conceptual ideas far more effectively, which will greatly help in building knowledge for students.

When students interact with technologies, it allows them to visualize the abstract, experiment with immediate feedback, and interact with resources that enhance classroom learning. For example, applications like GeoGebra and Desmos Graphing Calculator help students play with equations and immediately see how things change in a way that develops intuitive insights into powerful mathematical ideas, such as derivatives, integrals, and graph transformations.

GeoGebra, Desmos Graphing Calculator and many other applications are really powerful tools when it comes to the visualization of functions, calculus exploration, and solving algebraic equations.

Popular applications in applied mathematics are regression analysis apps, graphing calculators by Matlab, and SPSS tutorials, which give students a chance to perform data analysis, regression modeling, and explore statistical analyses.

Wolfram Alpha and Microsoft Math Solver can solve the most complex mathematical problems with proper explanation- ideal tools for homework and self-study purposes.

At a more general level of applied mathematics, something like Operation Research (OR) Simplex would be necessary to complete exercises using linear programming and optimization.

Also, probability calculators and statistics apps can enable students to calculate probability or carry out statistical analysis, test hypotheses, and interpret data.

Advanced topics involve Number Theory APK, GCD/LCM calculation, and other operations such as prime factorization, integer properties (perfect numbers, abundant, deficient), etc.

Testing and quiz applications like Google Forms with Quiz Mode and Microsoft Forms are quite helpful in conducting fast in-class testing through which teachers/professors can estimate the knowledge of students quite easily in real time.

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